

Operational biodiversity proxy indicators derived from LPIS and Earth Observation data: a transferable monitoring framework

Abstract

Monitoring biodiversity in agricultural landscapes remains constrained by a persistent disconnect between ecological theory and operational policy datasets. While Earth Observation (EO) and administrative systems such as the Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) and Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) provide high-resolution spatial data, they are not explicitly designed for biodiversity assessment. This study develops and applies a harmonised framework for deriving biodiversity-relevant proxies from LPIS, IACS, and Sentinel-2 time-series data, with a focus on arable land use diversity in Hungary. The framework operationalises landscape ecology concepts —particularly habitat connectivity, heterogeneity, and mosaicity — into parcel- and quadrat-level indicators that are directly computable within Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) monitoring infrastructures.

Using a decadal dataset (2015–2024), we construct three core indicators: (i) ecosystem connectivity based on land cover boundary length, (ii) compositional diversity integrating crop and land cover heterogeneity, and (iii) intra-parcel structural mosaicity derived from EO-based segmentation. Results reveal a systematic decline in boundary complexity between arable land and semi-natural landscape elements, alongside increasing spatial homogeneity in arable systems. Change detection analysis indicates that more than 80% of analysed quadrats exhibit significant reductions in connectivity over time, suggesting progressive landscape simplification.

The findings demonstrate that integrated EO–administrative data systems can generate scalable, reproducible proxies for biodiversity-relevant landscape structure. However, results also highlight the limitations of current proxy approaches, particularly their inability to directly observe species-level ecological processes. The study contributes a transferable methodological framework for operational biodiversity monitoring within CAP implementation systems and advances the integration of ecological theory into policy-relevant geospatial infrastructures.

Keywords: biodiversity proxies; landscape connectivity; habitat heterogeneity; arable land use; Earth Observation; LPIS; IACS; Sentinel-2; Common Agricultural Policy; agricultural landscape structure; spatial indicators; ecosystem monitoring

1 Introduction

Agricultural landscapes occupy a central position in European biodiversity policy due to their extensive spatial coverage and their dual role as providers of ecosystem services and major drivers of habitat transformation. They are therefore a key domain for assessing interactions between land management practices and ecological condition. Within the European Union, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) constitutes the primary framework regulating agricultural land use through financial incentives and compliance requirements. Its implementation relies on integrated administrative and geospatial infrastructures, most notably the Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS), which supports payment administration and eligibility verification, and associated parcel-level geospatial datasets used for CAP control and monitoring. These systems are designed for policy implementation rather than environmental

43 assessment, yet they generate high-resolution spatial data that can be reused for analytical
44 purposes beyond their original administrative scope.

45 In parallel, Earth Observation (EO) technologies have significantly enhanced the capacity to
46 monitor land surface dynamics at high spatial and temporal resolution. Sentinel-based satellite
47 systems now enable near-continuous observation of vegetation dynamics, land cover change,
48 and agricultural management practices across large spatial extents. Despite these advances, a
49 persistent gap remains between the richness of available spatial data and the ecological
50 indicators used for biodiversity assessment in agricultural landscapes. While EO and
51 administrative datasets provide detailed structural information, their direct translation into
52 ecologically meaningful metrics remains limited.

53 Landscape ecology provides a theoretical foundation for addressing this gap, particularly
54 through the concepts of habitat connectivity and heterogeneity as key determinants of species
55 distribution and ecosystem functioning. However, the operationalisation of these concepts in
56 applied monitoring frameworks remains fragmented. Existing indicators are often developed
57 independently of administrative geospatial infrastructures and rely on static land cover
58 representations, limiting their compatibility with EO-based time series and policy-oriented
59 monitoring systems.

60 A further constraint relates to the nature of biodiversity observability. Biodiversity is typically
61 assessed through species-level or habitat-quality metrics, which are not directly measurable
62 from either EO-derived land surface variables or administrative datasets. As a result,
63 operational approaches rely on proxy indicators that approximate ecological conditions through
64 landscape structure. These proxies are often methodologically heterogeneous, weakly
65 standardised, and difficult to transfer across regions and governance contexts. This issue is
66 particularly relevant in agricultural systems, where small-scale landscape elements such as
67 hedgerows, field margins, and isolated tree clusters play a disproportionately important
68 ecological role but are inconsistently represented in administrative land parcel systems.

69 This study addresses these limitations by developing a harmonised framework for constructing
70 biodiversity-relevant proxy indicators that integrate EO data with CAP administrative
71 geospatial datasets and landscape ecology theory. The central contribution lies in translating
72 habitat connectivity and landscape heterogeneity into spatially explicit indicators that can be
73 computed at parcel level using EO-derived time series and LPIS-compatible spatial structures.
74 This allows administrative geospatial infrastructures to be used as analytical foundations for
75 ecological interpretation without assuming that they were originally designed for environmental
76 monitoring.

77 The framework further refines conventional landscape metrics by adapting them to intensively
78 managed agricultural landscapes. It explicitly accounts for the prevalence of linear landscape
79 elements in administrative datasets and incorporates the ecological role of isolated semi-natural
80 features as potential stepping-stones in fragmented environments. This adjustment improves
81 the interpretability of connectivity and heterogeneity metrics in structurally simplified
82 agricultural systems dominated by arable land use.

83 Finally, the study advances the analysis of agricultural landscapes from static representations
84 towards dynamic, EO-enabled monitoring of structural change. By integrating administrative
85 and remote sensing data sources, the proposed framework enables continuous observation of
86 biodiversity-relevant landscape dynamics at parcel level, providing a scalable basis for
87 assessing spatial and temporal variability in agricultural ecosystem structure.

88 2 Background

89 2.1 Policy shift from conservation to restoration and monitoring 90 requirements

91 The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Performance-based Monitoring and Evaluation
92 Framework (PMEF), implemented across EU Member States since 2023, reflects a broader shift
93 towards result-oriented policy design, in which environmental and sustainability objectives are
94 assessed through structured indicators and monitoring systems embedded in CAP governance.
95 The framework strengthens the role of evidence-based evaluation of policy interventions using
96 harmonised indicator sets and spatially explicit reporting systems.

97 Within this evolving governance context, the Nature Restoration Law (NRL; Regulation (EU)
98 2024/1991) constitutes a binding extension of EU biodiversity policy. Its overarching objective
99 is to halt and reverse biodiversity loss while strengthening ecosystem resilience across
100 terrestrial and marine systems. The regulation explicitly recognises the importance of landscape
101 structure for ecological connectivity, including outside formally designated protected areas.

102 Member States are required to develop National Restoration Plans detailing how restoration
103 targets will be achieved, with initial submissions due by September 2026. Following approval,
104 implementation proceeds on a continuous basis, supported by structured monitoring and
105 reporting obligations. The European Commission is responsible for evaluation, while the
106 European Environment Agency (EEA) provides technical support through regular reporting,
107 including annual progress assessments and periodic reviews of ecosystem condition, policy
108 effectiveness, and implementation outcomes.

109 A central requirement of the NRL is the establishment of measurable trends in ecosystem
110 condition using biodiversity-related indicators. These indicators — defined as biological,
111 chemical, or physical parameters — are used to assess ecosystem structure, functioning, and
112 integrity. They support the identification of anthropogenic pressures, the evaluation of
113 ecosystem changes over time, and the spatial prioritisation of restoration measures. In
114 agricultural systems, where land-use intensity strongly influences ecological conditions,
115 spatially explicit indicators are particularly important for consistent monitoring and
116 comparability across regions.

117 The NRL further sets targets aimed at increasing the extent and ecological quality of high-
118 diversity landscape features in agricultural land, including buffer strips, field margins,
119 hedgerows, wooded strips, isolated trees, ditches, ponds, wetlands, and terraces. These features
120 contribute to structural complexity and landscape connectivity, facilitating species movement
121 and genetic exchange. In fragmented agricultural landscapes, linear elements such as
122 hedgerows and riparian vegetation function as key ecological corridors.

123 This study responds to these policy and monitoring requirements by developing harmonised
124 landscape feature datasets and analytical services to support implementation and evaluation
125 under the NRL. The proposed national-scale framework enables the identification of degraded
126 linear and patch elements, particularly in arable-dominated landscapes characterised by reduced
127 connectivity. In addition, change detection methods allow the assessment of degradation
128 trajectories and potential drivers, thereby supporting more targeted restoration planning.

129 Beyond structural restoration, the NRL also contributes to objectives under the Habitats
130 Directive and Birds Directive. Spatial indicators of land cover composition and configuration
131 can support assessment of habitat condition and suitability for threatened species. In addition,
132 landscape features contribute to ecosystem services such as water regulation, climate

133 moderation, pollination, and soil protection. While full ecosystem service quantification is
134 complex, partial indicators remain useful for policy implementation.

135 2.2 Landscape features as key elements of biodiversity in 136 agricultural landscapes

137 Landscape features (LFs) are permanent, non-productive natural or semi-natural elements
138 embedded in agricultural landscapes, including hedgerows, buffer strips, field margins, ponds,
139 wooded strips, small woodlands, and wetlands. Although spatially limited, they contribute
140 disproportionately to biodiversity and ecosystem services.

141 In intensively managed arable systems, LFs often represent the last remaining semi-natural
142 habitats within structurally simplified production landscapes. Their ecological role is therefore
143 inherently multidimensional (Fig. 1). They provide habitat for pollinators, birds, mammals, and
144 invertebrates while supporting species movement and reducing fragmentation.

145 Beyond biodiversity, LFs regulate microclimate through wind attenuation and temperature
146 buffering, reduce soil erosion through runoff regulation and soil stabilisation, and support
147 nutrient retention and water purification. Wet features regulate hydrological dynamics through
148 temporary water storage, that attenuate peak flows. Woody elements additionally contribute to
149 carbon sequestration and, in some cases, biomass provision, while linear woody structures may
150 act as ecological barriers limiting disease transmission and cross-pollination.

151
152 *Figure 1. Ecosystem services provided by landscape features (own elaboration)*

153 Within the CAP (2023–2027), LFs are explicitly recognised as instruments for achieving
154 environmental objectives. They cover approximately 5.6% of EU agricultural land (Fig. 2) (EC,
155 2024) and are integrated into conditionality requirements and eco-schemes.

156 Despite their policy recognition, the definition and classification of LFs have evolved unevenly
157 across Member States since their formal inclusion in Good Agricultural and Environmental
158 Condition (GAEC) standards in 2009. Classification schemes are typically functional, whereas
159 in this study a phenological typology is adopted to align with Earth Observation (EO)
160 detectability. This distinguishes woody features (e.g. hedgerows, tree lines, riparian vegetation),
161 grassy features (e.g. field margins), wet features (e.g. ponds, ditches, wetlands), and stony or
162 cultural elements (e.g. stone walls, mounds).

Figure 2: Estimates of Landscape Features shares in agricultural land by MS (% and standard deviation). The horizontal blue line represents the EU average. (EC, 2024)

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166 LFs are integrated across multiple CAP instruments. Under conditionality, particularly GAEC
 167 8, farmers are required to retain existing features. Eco-schemes under Pillar 1 provide annual
 168 incentives for enhanced management, while agri-environment-climate measures under Pillar 2
 169 support multiannual restoration and creation. However, despite this policy architecture,
 170 implementation remains heterogeneous across Member States, reflecting differences in
 171 administrative capacity, data availability, and monitoring infrastructure.

172 A key limitation concerns monitoring. CAP Indicator I.21 measures the share of utilised
 173 agricultural area (UAA) covered by landscape features, but is derived from the Geospatial Aid
 174 Application and therefore includes only features declared under CAP support schemes. This
 175 leads to systematic underestimation of LF occurrence and reveals a structural mismatch
 176 between reported policy data and actual landscape conditions.

177 From an ecosystem service perspective, the value of LFs is highly context-dependent. Naturally
 178 occurring features are primarily valued for biodiversity support, connectivity, and carbon
 179 storage, whereas anthropogenic features often generate indirect production benefits, such as
 180 enhanced pollination or crop protection. In pollinator-limited systems, for example, flowering
 181 field margins can simultaneously increase biodiversity and improve agricultural output. The
 182 marginal ecological value of LFs is particularly high in simplified, intensively cultivated
 183 landscapes, where even small or isolated elements can function as stepping stones for species
 184 dispersal.

185 Despite sustained policy attention, the effectiveness of LFs implementation is constrained by
 186 persistent data and monitoring limitations, particularly their incomplete representation within
 187 Area Monitoring Systems. This has led to uneven uptake and, in some cases, declining
 188 implementation momentum, underscoring the need for improved harmonised datasets and
 189 stronger integration within CAP–IACS GIS infrastructures.

190 These structural and data-related limitations create a clear need for alternative approaches
 191 capable of capturing ecological structure and function at scale. In particular, there is a growing
 192 requirement for spatially explicit indicators that translate landscape composition and
 193 configuration into measurable proxies of biodiversity. Addressing this challenge requires robust
 194 metrics that can operationalise ecological processes using observable land surface patterns
 195 derived from Earth Observation. Recent advances in EO technologies — including high-
 196 resolution multispectral and multi-temporal satellite imagery, cloud computing infrastructures,
 197 and IoT integration — now enable continuous, full-coverage monitoring of agricultural parcels
 198 at national scale. This transition from fragmented reporting to operational, data-driven

199 monitoring frameworks is essential for bridging the current gap between policy objectives and
200 measurable biodiversity outcomes within the CAP and related environmental frameworks.

201 2.3 Biodiversity proxies in agricultural landscapes

202 Connectivity is essential for maintaining genetic diversity and enabling recolonisation
203 following local disturbances (Hufnagel & Mics, 2022). However, the relationship between
204 connectivity and biodiversity is non-linear and context-dependent. While classical ecological
205 theory emphasises the importance of connectivity, recent evidence suggests that total habitat
206 area may, in some cases, be a stronger predictor of species richness than corridor configuration
207 alone (Rybicki et al., 2019). Under conditions of high habitat availability, fragmentation may
208 even increase local diversity by reducing competitive exclusion, whereas in highly simplified
209 landscapes with limited habitat, connectivity becomes critical to prevent local extinctions
210 (Rybicki et al., 2019).

211 Remote sensing has increasingly been used to quantify how landscape structure, connectivity,
212 and biodiversity jointly influence broader ecosystem processes, including carbon and water
213 cycling (Gomasca et al., 2024).

214 A complementary and widely used concept is habitat heterogeneity, typically operationalised
215 through the Habitat Heterogeneity Index (HHI). This metric captures variation in habitat types
216 and spatial configuration within a landscape, thereby providing an indirect measure of
217 ecological niche availability. Higher habitat heterogeneity generally supports greater species
218 richness by increasing environmental variability and the number of available niches.

219 Advances in remote sensing and GIS have fundamentally transformed the estimation of such
220 metrics, enabling large-scale, spatially explicit biodiversity assessments that were previously
221 unattainable through field-based surveys alone. This shift reflects a transition from static
222 categorical land cover representations towards near real-time classification of satellite image
223 time series and the derivation of continuous structural landscape indices.

224 The operational workflow for HHI estimation typically includes data acquisition and
225 preprocessing, machine learning-based classification, land cover aggregation, and spatial
226 metric computation. In addition, texture-based approaches such as the Gray-Level Co-
227 occurrence Matrix (GLCM) are applied in cases where habitat boundaries are not clearly
228 defined, as they quantify spatial variability directly from pixel-level spectral information
229 without prior classification.

230 A range of established indices is used to quantify landscape heterogeneity, each capturing
231 different structural dimensions. Shape complexity metrics, such as Patton's index (Patton,
232 1975), describe the geometric irregularity of patches and are commonly interpreted in terms of
233 edge effects. Although such measures provide valuable information on spatial configuration,
234 they can disproportionately emphasise linear features such as grass margins. In intensively
235 cultivated arable landscapes, this may introduce bias by overstating the ecological contribution
236 of narrow, highly prevalent elements while underrepresenting isolated features such as tree
237 groups, which often function as more effective ecological stepping stones. For this reason,
238 shape complexity weighting is not applied in the present framework.

239 In contrast, compositional diversity is captured through land cover diversity indices such as the
240 Shannon–Wiener and Simpson indices, which quantify heterogeneity based on proportional
241 area of habitat types. The Shannon index is defined as (H'): $H' = -\sum p_i \ln p_i$, while the Simpson
242 index is expressed as (D): $D = 1 / \sum p_i^2$, where p_i represents the proportional cover of habitat type
243 i . These metrics are applied both at parcel level and across aggregated land cover mosaics,
244 providing scalable measures of landscape diversity.

245 Structural heterogeneity can also be assessed using field-based transect methods, originally
246 developed by Moe and Wegge (1994), which quantify landscape patchiness as the number of
247 habitat transitions per unit distance. Although not inherently a GIS method, this approach can
248 be operationalised within machine learning frameworks and is particularly relevant because it
249 aligns with field protocols used for pollinator and butterfly monitoring under biodiversity
250 assessment schemes.

251 The relationship between heterogeneity and connectivity is inherently complex. While each of
252 these indices captures a distinct dimension of landscape structure, their interpretation must
253 account for trade-offs between heterogeneity and connectivity. Heterogeneous landscapes often
254 function as ecological mosaics that facilitate movement of generalist species through stepping-
255 stone habitats. However, excessive fragmentation may reduce functional connectivity for
256 specialist species requiring large, contiguous habitat patches, effectively turning high
257 heterogeneity into a dispersal barrier.

258 This duality reflects a structural trade-off: homogeneous landscapes support specialist species
259 dependent on continuous habitats but provide limited niche diversity, whereas heterogeneous
260 landscapes support greater niche availability and edge effects but may reduce connectivity for
261 specialists. At the same time, heterogeneous systems often exhibit greater ecological resilience
262 due to increased habitat diversity and potential refugia.

263 Overall, habitat heterogeneity and connectivity represent complementary and highly
264 informative spatial proxies for biodiversity. They can be effectively quantified using Earth
265 Observation and GIS-based methodologies, which enable large-scale assessment of landscape
266 structure through classification, spatial metrics, and time-series analysis (Gomasca et al.,
267 2024). Commonly applied indices include shape complexity measures (Patton, 1975), Shannon
268 diversity metrics (Magurran, 2004), Simpson diversity indices (Maskell et al., 2019), and
269 transect-based heterogeneity measures (Moe & Wegge, 1994), while texture-based approaches
270 such as GLCM remain particularly valuable in landscapes lacking clear structural boundaries.

271 2.4 Conceptual novelty

272 Despite widespread application of connectivity and heterogeneity metrics in landscape ecology,
273 existing approaches are predominantly (i) descriptive and static, focusing on landscape
274 composition, or (ii) disconnected from operational policy monitoring systems. Biodiversity
275 proxy frameworks are rarely designed for direct integration with administrative land parcel
276 systems such as IACS/LPIS or with Earth Observation-based Area Monitoring infrastructures.

277 This study addresses this gap by operationalising biodiversity proxies within a harmonised,
278 parcel-level Earth Observation framework. Connectivity and heterogeneity are translated into
279 spatially explicit indicators directly computable from EO-derived land cover dynamics and
280 administrative geospatial structures, enabling integration within CAP implementation
281 infrastructures.

282 Furthermore, the framework distinguishes compositional and functional interpretations of
283 heterogeneity in intensively managed agricultural landscapes and adjusts classical metrics to
284 reduce bias towards linear features prevalent in administrative datasets. This is particularly
285 relevant in arable systems where isolated semi-natural elements function as critical ecological
286 stepping stones but are often underrepresented in conventional indices.

287 Finally, the framework shifts analysis from static landscape description to dynamic monitoring
288 of biodiversity-relevant structural change, enabling continuous temporal tracking of landscape
289 patterns and supporting transition towards operational ecological monitoring.

290 2.5 GIS approaches and administrative datasets

291 Administrative datasets such as the Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) and the Integrated
292 Administration and Control System (IACS) represent a unique, policy-relevant data
293 infrastructure for environmental monitoring and agricultural land analysis. These systems
294 provide high-resolution, georeferenced information that is directly embedded in the
295 implementation of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), thereby offering a strong basis for
296 linking environmental assessment with policy monitoring. Fig. 3. illustrates the interoperability
297 between remote sensing pipelines, administrative geospatial systems, and CAP policy
298 monitoring mechanisms underpinning operational biodiversity proxy development

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300

301 *Figure 3: Conceptual architecture of the CAP Area Monitoring System (AMS) ecosystem:*
302 *integration of Earth Observation, IACS–LPIS infrastructure, and policy evaluation*
303 *components (since 2023)*

304 The annual Geospatial Aid Application (GSA) provides parcel-level crop information across
305 the EU at approximately 1:5,000 mapping scale. Data quality is centrally verified by the
306 European Commission's Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development (DG
307 AGRI) through a standardised, annually applied and ISO-compatible validation methodology.
308 However, the GSA primarily reflects declared agricultural activity linked to direct payments,
309 which introduces structural limitations in terms of completeness and ecological
310 representativeness.

311 The Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) complements this dataset by providing human-
312 validated information on land cover and landscape features at a similar spatial resolution. In
313 some Member States, such as Hungary, the LPIS (MePAR) operates as a wall-to-wall dataset
314 that integrates CAP-relevant land cover and land use classifications. It is typically updated on
315 a three-year cycle based on orthophoto interpretation and is further validated through annual
316 checks using Earth Observation-based outputs from the Area Monitoring System. However,
317 such wall-to-wall implementations remain rare across the EU, despite their strong potential for

318 enabling full landscape-level analyses, including the assessment of ecosystem connectivity
319 across both natural and semi-natural areas.

320 The Area Monitoring System (AMS), integrated within IACS, provides a complementary
321 satellite-based monitoring infrastructure that supports continuous, parcel-level observation of
322 agricultural activity. It enables systematic and automated tracking of crop types and
323 management practices through time, supported by dense satellite image time series. Within this
324 framework, AMS allows the derivation of several biodiversity-relevant variables, including
325 crop type variability, vegetation dynamics, bare soil exposure, waterlogging events, and spatial
326 relationships such as adjacency and connectivity between land cover types.

327 Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery plays a central role in this system by enabling high-frequency
328 monitoring of vegetation dynamics. The Level-2A product, in particular, provides surface
329 reflectance data suitable for time-series analysis and large-scale spatial modelling (Gomasca
330 et al., 2024). Despite these advances, important limitations remain. These include incomplete
331 crop declaration within the GSA in certain contexts, as not all managed parcels are included in
332 direct payment systems, as well as the limited ecological interpretability of administrative
333 classifications when used in isolation. From a biodiversity perspective, this limitation is
334 particularly relevant. Traditional biodiversity assessment relies on species-level metrics that are
335 not directly observable in IACS or EO datasets (Magurran, 2004). Therefore, a key challenge
336 is to assess the extent to which biodiversity can be approximated using proxy indicators derived
337 from these data sources.

338 This study investigates the informational capacity of LPIS/IACS and EO data for biodiversity
339 monitoring, focusing on parcel-level operationalisation. The AMS is interpreted not only as a
340 compliance tool but as an emerging infrastructure for modelling land use dynamics relevant to
341 biodiversity, climate, and soil objectives. However, species-level processes remain
342 unobservable, reinforcing the need for carefully designed proxy-based approaches.

343 **3 Materials and methods**

344 **3.1 Conceptual framework and hypotheses**

345 Our approach builds on the assumption that increased adjacency between different land cover
346 types, expressed as boundary length, is a structural proxy for habitat heterogeneity and, by
347 extension, biodiversity potential (Patton, 1975; Tews et al., 2004). These spatial configurations
348 represent observable outcomes of complex ecological systems, even if direct causal pathways
349 between land use and biodiversity cannot always be explicitly resolved. Nevertheless, robust
350 indicative relationships and system-level trends can be identified (Rybicki et al., 2019).

351 We address the central research question of how meaningful biodiversity-related indicators can
352 be derived to differentiate agricultural parcels within a benchmarking framework that is both
353 operational and policy-relevant. Such a system is intended to support national administrations
354 in redirecting agricultural payments towards areas that deliver higher ecosystem value, while
355 simultaneously guiding intensification towards less ecologically sensitive regions. We therefore
356 conceptualise increased adjacency length between neighbouring ecosystem types not only as a
357 signal of fragmentation, but also as an indicator of structural diversity and potential landscape
358 stability.

359 A second key question concerns how to approximate biodiversity impacts arising from spatial
360 and temporal configurations of land use and land cover. In this regard, we focus on
361 phenologically observable outputs of coupled socio-ecological systems rather than attempting

362 to reconstruct underlying causal mechanisms. While causality cannot be fully established at this
363 level of observation, consistent patterns and indicator-based proxies of biodiversity change can
364 be derived.

365 Our analytical framework operates across three nested spatial levels. First, all variables are
366 assessed at the agricultural parcel level as the primary unit of observation. Second, parcel-level
367 indicators are aggregated to farm level to capture management-scale patterns. Third, these
368 indicators are further generalised to quadrat and regional scales, enabling scalable spatial
369 comparison and national-level assessment.

370 3.2 Data infrastructure and analytical workflow

371 The analysis is conducted across agri-dominant quadrats covering the entire national territory,
372 with a hierarchical structure linking agricultural parcels, quadrats, and regional aggregates. We
373 integrate three core data systems, each contributing distinct spatial, thematic, and temporal
374 information layers.

375 The Hungarian Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS; MePAR) provides a wall-to-wall,
376 nationally consistent land cover dataset aligned with the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)
377 payment structure. The dataset is produced at a 1:5,000 mapping scale and covers both eligible
378 and non-eligible areas. It is derived from orthophotos updated approximately every three years,
379 and multi-temporal satellite imagery. Land cover classification follows CAP categories,
380 including arable land, permanent grassland, plantations, and non-agricultural eligible areas,
381 while non-eligible zones are classified primarily based on vegetation dominance. The minimum
382 mapping unit (MMU) is 100 m² for arable land and 300 m² for permanent grassland, while
383 linear landscape elements are explicitly captured where they exceed a minimum width of
384 approximately two metres. This wall-to-wall structure is relatively unique within the EU
385 context, where many Member States rely instead on Copernicus High Resolution Layers or
386 INSPIRE-compatible ecosystem datasets.

387 The Geospatial Aid Application (GSA) complements LPIS by providing annually declared
388 agricultural parcel geometries linked to CAP payments. In the Hungarian case, GSA does not
389 fully cover all agricultural land, as only parcels above 2,500 m² and formally submitted by
390 farmers are included. At the time of analysis, these declarations are not fully validated against
391 independent external datasets, meaning that positional and thematic inconsistencies may persist.
392 However, this limitation is progressively addressed through the introduction of monitoring-
393 based control systems under the Area Monitoring System (AMS), which increasingly rely on
394 remote sensing-derived crop probability layers.

395 Sentinel-2 multispectral time series constitute the third core data source. These data enable near-
396 weekly observation of vegetation dynamics across large spatial extents. We use the Level-2A
397 (MSIL2A) product (surface reflectance), incorporating ten spectral bands spanning visible,
398 near-infrared, and shortwave infrared domains. Cloud contamination is addressed through
399 temporal compositing enabled by the high revisit frequency of the platform. Geometric
400 correction is performed using the Copernicus DEM GLO-90m digital surface model. Data are
401 obtained from the Copernicus Open Access Hub, ensuring reproducibility and consistency
402 across the study period.

403 Together, these datasets form an integrated analytical workflow that links structural land cover
404 information, administrative declarations, and dynamic biophysical signals, thereby enabling
405 multi-source ecosystem indicator construction.

3.3 Operationalisation of biodiversity proxies

We operationalise the assessment of biodiversity indirectly through a set of spatial and temporal proxies derived from land use configuration and vegetation dynamics. This approach is grounded in the observation that arable land exerts the dominant influence on agroecosystem structure and adjacent semi-natural habitats. Consequently, remotely sensed time series provide a scalable means of capturing system-wide ecological variability across multiple temporal windows.

Using the Area Monitoring System framework, we extract indicators that reflect both land surface dynamics and ecosystem service functionality. These include temporal variability in crop composition, intra-annual dynamics of vegetation cover, duration and distribution of bare soil exposure, the temporal distribution of stubble management operations, disturbance events such as crop failure due to waterlogging, and management-driven processes such as harvesting and mowing cycles. We further capture adjacency structures between land cover classes, distinguishing between patchy, linear, and aggregated configurations, as well as associated ecosystem service functions such as buffering capacity, erosion control, connectivity, and water retention.

Based on these observations, we define three primary indicator groups at quadrat level. The first captures ecosystem connectivity through the total boundary length between land cover classes derived from LPIS data, measured in metres and updated annually. The second reflects land cover diversity and compositional variability, integrating both LPIS-derived categories and crop types observed in GSA or remote sensing-derived crop probability maps. The third describes spatial mosaicity and structural homogeneity of arable systems, derived from Sentinel-2 time series segmentation at approximately 20 m spatial resolution, expressed as the mean area of homogeneous vegetation units.

A key methodological challenge lies in data interoperability, as differences in thematic classification, spatial resolution, and temporal updating cycles must be harmonised into a coherent analytical framework. In this study, we develop a harmonised categorisation scheme based on Hungarian LPIS data and validate its transferability using Austrian IACS datasets available under INSPIRE standards. This enables cross-country applicability of the proposed indicator system.

The resulting ecosystem indicator flowchart integrates GIS and Earth Observation data streams into a unified analytical structure for biodiversity assessment (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Flowchart of deriving ecosystem indicators based on the inter-operability of the available GIS databases and the EO data

441 This framework establishes impact-oriented indicators to assess the effects of CAP measures
442 on habitat complexity and landscape diversity, thereby providing indirect evidence of changes
443 in species diversity, population dynamics, and ecosystem stability in agricultural systems. At
444 national scale, the approach demonstrates how existing geospatial data infrastructures can be
445 integrated to support multi-annual analyses of biodiversity trends, ecosystem service provision,
446 and the dynamics of habitat structure and stability.

447 The boundary length indicator is particularly sensitive to changes in linear elements of the
448 ecological network, as these features exhibit high perimeter-to-area ratios in LPIS-derived
449 datasets. In contrast, compact or island-like natural vegetation within croplands is less strongly
450 represented by this metric; consequently, such elements require differentiated interpretation and,
451 where appropriate, complementary weighting based on the full LPIS dataset. The framework
452 further enables spatially explicit and comparative assessment of habitat elements across
453 agricultural landscapes, supporting consistent evaluation of heterogeneity and connectivity
454 patterns.

455 3.4 The power of multi-annual data comparison

456 We analyse a decadal dataset spanning 2015–2024, with particular emphasis on the structural
457 consistency of LPIS data in the later years of the series. For the final three years of the study
458 period, changes in LPIS land cover polygons no longer introduce systematic bias, enabling
459 more robust temporal comparisons.

460 Our assessment shows that, at national level, the MePAR (LPIS) classification methodology
461 has remained stable since 2018. Observed differences are therefore not attributable to
462 refinements in the delineation of eligible areas or to changes in classification schemes, but
463 instead reflect actual dynamics in land use and land cover.

464 To ensure temporal comparability, we adopt a multi-annual aggregation approach rather than
465 relying on single-year observations. Specifically, we compare the five-year average for 2018–
466 2022 with the average for 2023–2024. This distinction is necessary because, from 2023 onwards,
467 linear landscape elements with high biodiversity relevance—particularly tree rows (code 180)
468 and field margins (code 183)—are systematically represented across the full national coverage
469 within the natural vegetation category. This harmonised representation supports consistent
470 inter-year comparison while enabling more reliable trend analysis.

471 3.5 Classification of LPIS land cover categories based on 472 phenological characteristics

473 The Hungarian LPIS (MePAR) land cover dataset is primarily derived from remote sensing
474 data through expert visual interpretation, complemented by administrative requirements linked
475 to CAP area-based support schemes. As a consequence, the dataset includes only those
476 vegetation phenological categories and environmental variables that are either consistently
477 distinguishable in orthophotos and satellite imagery or explicitly required as national vector
478 layers for eligibility control. From a habitat perspective, this results in varying levels of thematic
479 detail across land cover classes.

480 The classification of land cover is therefore determined by the detectability of phenological and
481 structural characteristics in remote sensing data. These include woody vegetation and the
482 fragmentation of agricultural land use; built-up areas, non-vegetated elements, and permanent
483 water bodies; the presence of water in vegetation, soils, and open surfaces; exposed soil
484 surfaces; green vegetation and biomass quantity; and vegetation type as inferred from spectral
485 reflectance differences.

486 These observable characteristics are further constrained by the spatial resolution of satellite
487 imagery and the temporal dynamics of vegetation development, including patterns such as row
488 spacing, crop structure, ploughing direction, and seasonal variation. As a result, certain land
489 cover categories are aggregated or generalised to ensure consistency and detectability within
490 the available data. Importantly, any differentiation between categories implies a shift in habitat
491 type; consequently, changes in land cover classification directly reflect changes in landscape
492 mosaic structure and associated edge effects, which are relevant proxies for biodiversity
493 dynamics.

494 To support the analysis of temporal changes and to enable consistent weighting of contributions
495 to biodiversity and ecosystem services, we aggregate LPIS land cover classes into four principal
496 categories: arable land (A), natural vegetation (N), semi-natural vegetation including managed
497 permanent grasslands (SN), and artificial sealed surfaces (AS). This harmonised classification
498 provides a consistent analytical basis for tracking annual dynamics in land cover composition
499 and structure.

500 3.6 Calculating the ecosystem connectivity indicator

501 We quantify ecosystem connectivity through the total length of boundaries between different
502 land cover categories within each UTM quadrat. This metric describes the complexity of spatial
503 patterns formed by the intersections of these boundaries within a given sampling unit (Fig. 5).
504 The use of boundary length as an indicator is based on the assumption that higher diversity
505 values occur along habitat transitions; therefore, the greater the total boundary length between
506 land cover categories within a given area, the more diverse—and consequently more
507 favourable—the habitat conditions are.

508 The GIS analysis includes 27 land cover groups derived from the LPIS (MePAR) dataset. For
509 each quadrat, we compute the length of all boundary combinations between land cover classes,
510 excluding self-intersections. This allows not only the derivation of an aggregated connectivity
511 indicator but also the explicit identification and verification of which land cover types intersect,
512 and at what lengths, within each spatial unit.

513

514 *Figure 5. The MePAR land cover data, filtered by the designated UTM quadrants*
515 *—1,255,000 polygons per year—constitutes the input data for the boundary length*
516 *calculation.*

517 *The four highlighted quadrats clearly demonstrate how significant the differences can be*
518 *even between neighbouring quadrats.*

519 The indicator is presented as an aggregated value at UTM quadrat level. It accounts for all
520 eligible and non-eligible land cover types, while excluding built-up areas and linear
521 infrastructure elements characterised by artificial surfaces. Although several alternative
522 aggregation approaches could be applied, we adopt a gridded (UTM quadrat) framework, as
523 this spatial resolution aligns with the scale of available field observation data and enables
524 consistent comparison.

525 Geospatial data were prepared and analysed using the open-source software QuantumGIS
526 (QGIS). Land cover datasets were imported into a PostGIS database, where spatial queries were
527 executed to calculate adjacency relationships and boundary lengths. QGIS was subsequently
528 used for map production, while aggregated indicator values and associated analyses were
529 further processed in MS Office Excel.

530 The aggregated indicator is derived through adjacency analysis of individual land cover
531 polygons. This enables the boundary lengths to be queried and analysed according to specific
532 combinations of neighbouring land cover types. For example, the analysis allows the extraction
533 of boundary lengths between cultivated permanent grasslands (LCC code 120, grazing and
534 mowing) and their surrounding land cover categories. In Fig. 6 the boundaries marked in white
535 show the adjacency of all LCC classes, of which the boundaries marked in blue are connected
536 to the permanent grassland within the analyzed quadrat.

537 *Figure 6. The length of the intersection of cultivated grasslands and other land cover*
 538 *categories - blue line. In the background on Sentinel-2 space image, April 02, 2019, false*
 539 *colour composite with R =7 G=8 B=3 band allocation*

540 3.7 Variability of crops and crop management techniques

541 This indicator captures the diversity of agricultural land use by combining land cover categories
 542 with the occurrence of arable crop types within each quadrat. It integrates information on
 543 agricultural, natural, and semi-natural land cover classes together with crop-type data derived
 544 from the Geospatial Aid Application (GSA).

545 For each quadrat, a single aggregated value is calculated as the sum of the number of distinct
 546 land cover category types—excluding built-up and infrastructure areas—and the number of
 547 crop types recorded in the annual GSA dataset. The indicator reflects the presence of different
 548 category types rather than their frequency. For example, multiple occurrences of the same
 549 category (e.g. several cultivated grassland parcels) are counted once, thereby representing
 550 compositional variation rather than area-based dominance.

551 This formulation enables the measurement of diversity shifts through the occurrence of different
 552 land cover and crop-type combinations, while maintaining comparability with the ecosystem
 553 connectivity indicator described in Section 3.6. The spatial complexity of how these categories
 554 are arranged within the quadrat is not captured directly by this metric, but is instead represented
 555 through the boundary-length-based connectivity indicator (Indicator A).

556 An illustrative example of the combined land cover and crop-type diversity calculation is
 557 provided for the Dévaványa sample area (Fig. 7), where the aggregated value reflects the joint
 558 occurrence of multiple land cover classes and arable crop types within a single quadrat.

559
 560 *Figure 7 Composite land cover and crop-type diversity indicator at quadrat level (Dévaványa*
 561 *sample area)*

562 3.8 Mosaicity and homogeneity of arable land cultivation

563 throughout the year

564 The heterogeneity index describes the degree of spatial homogeneity of vegetation within arable
 565 parcels over the full annual cycle. The analysis follows actual vegetation development, based
 566 on time series of Earth Observation (EO) data, and identifies homogeneous surface-cover units
 567 at a spatial resolution of 10 metres using Sentinel-2 imagery.

568 Homogeneous units are delineated through image analysis of Sentinel-2 time series that
 569 continuously track vegetation dynamics. The segmentation is performed on multi-band raster
 570 data derived from principal component transformation, which serves as the input to the image
 571 processing algorithm (see data preparation for details). Fig 8 illustrates the resulting
 572 segmentation of arable areas, with the transformed raster data shown in the background.

573 *Figure 8 Mapping the homogeneity of arable land using the segmentation method*

574 The pixel-level segmentation groups areas with similar surface cover, enabling the sensitive
 575 detection of within-parcel variability. This includes weeding inhomogeneities, differences in
 576 plant development due to drought conditions, saline patches, and partial mowing patterns in
 577 fodder crops.

578 The resulting homogeneous units do not correspond directly to the agricultural parcels defined
 579 in the Geospatial Aid Application. Areas that are cultivated as a single unit but declared as
 580 separate parcels within IACS are treated as one homogeneous unit when vegetation patterns
 581 indicate consistent development. Conversely, areas that are managed together initially but
 582 exhibit divergent phenological characteristics over time are classified as separate units.

583 4 Results

584 In this section we present the results of the national-scale application of the proposed framework
 585 to Hungarian agricultural landscapes, summarising spatial and temporal patterns of ecosystem
 586 connectivity, compositional diversity, and structural heterogeneity derived from LPIS and Earth
 587 Observation data across the full study period.

588 **4.1 Measuring ecosystem diversity using the connectivity index**
589 **based on land cover adjacency length**

590 Spatially explicit connectivity patterns are derived from LPIS-based land cover adjacency
591 analysis, with results mapped across multiple years of the full observation period (2023–2024).
592 We illustrate spatial distributions for 2023 and 2024 as representative examples (Fig.9), while
593 the full dataset enables annual tracking of connectivity dynamics over time.

594 Connectivity is defined as the total boundary length between land cover categories and is
595 visualised using 10 equal intervals. Boundary length values (in meters) are normalised and
596 classified into 10 categories per year to ensure comparability across the time series. The number
597 of quadrats per class is reported in parentheses in the legend.

598 Fig 9 shows the length of boundaries between different land cover types (m), aggregated at
599 grid-cell level for 2023 and 2024.

600

601

602 *Figure 9 Length of boundaries between different land cover types (m), aggregated by grid cell*
 603 *– 2023 and 2024.*

604 **4.2 Analysis of relationships between key land-cover categories**

605 Beyond total boundary length across all land cover classes, we derive national-level statistics
 606 for three analytically relevant land-cover interaction types, selected due to their ecological
 607 significance.

608 First, we quantify the total length of outer boundaries between arable land and linear landscape
 609 elements, including field margins, grassy or shrubby field edges, tree rows, and narrow forest
 610 strips. These features are critical for ecological network stability and habitat connectivity.

611 Second, we measure the total outer boundary length of arable land within each quadrat,
 612 independent of adjacent land cover type. This indicator captures the structural concentration of
 613 arable land. A reduction in boundary length indicates either field consolidation or removal of
 614 linear landscape features, while total arable area remains unchanged. Conversely, an increase
 615 reflects field subdivision or restoration of internal landscape features.

616 Third, we compute the total boundary length between all agricultural land (arable, grassland,
 617 orchards) and natural or semi-natural vegetation (excluding built-up areas). This indicator
 618 captures landscape mosaic structure and the degree of fragmentation between managed and
 619 semi-natural ecosystems.

620 These indicators are reported for 2021 and 2024, with equivalent time series available for earlier
 621 years. Fig. 10 shows the total boundary length between MePAR arable land and linear landscape
 622 features aggregated by quadrats for 2021 and 2024. Fig. 11 presents total arable land boundary
 623 length irrespective of adjacent land cover type for the same years. Fig. 12 shows the combined
 624 perimeter of agricultural land and natural/semi-natural vegetation, excluding built-up areas, as
 625 defined in LPIS-LCC classification.

626

627 *Figure 10 – Total length of MePAR arable land cover and the outer boundaries of linear*
 628 *landscape features (field edges, field margins, tree rows, narrow field-protecting forest strips)*
 629 *aggregated by quadrats – year 2021 and 2024.*

630

631

632

Figure 11 Total length of the outer boundary of the MePAR arable land cover by quadrats, regardless of the type of adjacent LCC, in 2021 and 2024

633

634

635

636

Figure 12 Total length of the perimeter of agricultural land (arable land + grassland + orchards) and natural and semi-natural vegetation (excluding built-up areas), as defined by the LPIS-LCC by quadrats in years 2021 and 2024.

637 The results show a clear decrease in boundary length between arable land and linear landscape
 638 elements from 2021 to 2024, as reflected in the shift in mean values.

639 The distribution is left-skewed and includes extreme values, indicating that spatial
 640 configurations of arable land are substantially less complex than those of mixed agricultural
 641 landscapes. This pattern is consistent with earlier policy interventions under greening measures,
 642 which aimed to preserve and enhance landscape elements embedded in arable systems.

643 The results are available for all years, and multi-year averages can be computed. Overall, the
 644 indicators relating arable land boundaries to other LCC categories, particularly linear landscape
 645 elements, provide robust baseline measures. Year-to-year deviations therefore serve as direct
 646 indicators of changes in landscape structure and, by extension, biodiversity-relevant landscape
 647 complexity.

648 4.3 Categorisation of spatial complexity of agriculture-dominated 649 quadrats

650 The connectivity dataset enables the classification of agriculture-dominated quadrats into
 651 spatial complexity classes based on mean and standard deviation thresholds (Table 1). These
 652 classes are used both as a basis for comparative temporal analysis and for identifying potential
 653 targets for policy intervention measures.

654 For agriculture-dominated quadrats, the classification thresholds are defined using a six-year
 655 reference period (2016–2021). Three spatial complexity categories are distinguished: values
 656 below the standard deviation from the mean (unfavourable spatial complexity), values within
 657 the standard deviation interval (average spatial complexity), and values above one standard
 658 deviation (favourable spatial complexity).

659 *Table 1. Classification of agriculture-dominated quadrats based on standard deviation–*
 660 *derived spatial complexity thresholds (2016–2021 reference period) and temporal distribution*
 661 *for 2022–2024*

Categories of spatial complexity	Standard deviation-based thresholds (6-year average, 2016-2021)	Quadrat numbers and percentages					
		2022		2023		2024	
Unfavourable / most vulnerable	< 99,6 km (<100 km)	537	14.17 %	429	11.32%	438	11.56%
Favourable	>208,9 km (>210 km)	632	16.68 %	630	16.63%	618	16.31%
Average	99,6-208,9 km (100-210 km)	2,620	69.15 %	2,730	72.05%	2,733	72.13%
Total		3,789	100.00 %	3,789	100.00 %	3,789	100.00 %

662 To ensure temporal comparability, fixed thresholds are applied consistently across years when
 663 the objective is to track shifts in category membership and direction of change. Under this
 664 approach, spatial complexity is classified into: (i) unfavourable (below standard deviation), (ii)
 665 average (within standard deviation interval), and (iii) favourable (above standard deviation).
 666 The results for 2022–2024 indicate a slight but consistent redistribution of quadrats, with a
 667 decrease in the proportion of unfavourable classes and a relatively stable share of favourable
 668 classes.

669 In parallel, an alternative classification approach is applied when the objective is spatial
 670 targeting of interventions. In this case, category boundaries are derived dynamically from the

671 statistical distribution of the current year. Jenks natural breaks optimisation (Jenks
 672 optimisation) is used to minimise within-class variance and maximise between-class variance,
 673 thereby identifying statistically coherent groupings within the data. This approach is
 674 particularly relevant for adaptive spatial planning, as it allows class definitions to reflect annual
 675 distributional changes in connectivity values. However, it also implies that class boundaries
 676 vary between years and must therefore be interpreted with caution in longitudinal comparisons.

677 In Table 2, for 2023 and 2024, dynamically derived thresholds show shifts in class boundaries
 678 that reflect changes in the national distribution of connectivity values. This supports a
 679 complementary use of static and dynamic classification depending on analytical purpose.

680 *Table 2. Year-specific spatial complexity classification of agriculture-dominated quadrats*
 681 *based on dynamically derived (Jenks) threshold values for 2023 and 2024*

<i>Categories of spatial complexity</i>	<i>Threshold (km/quadrat) 2023</i>	<i>Quadrat (nr) 2023</i>	<i>Quadrat (%) 2023</i>	<i>Threshold 2024</i>	<i>Quadrat (nr) 2024</i>	<i>Quadrat (%) 2024</i>
<i>Unfavourable / most vulnerable</i>	0-127	1,277	31.39%	0-136	1,341	35.39%
<i>Favourable</i>	127-198	1,961	48.21%	136-202	1,699	44.84%
<i>Average</i>	198-404	830	20.40%	202-407	749	19.77%
<i>Total</i>		4,068	100.00%		3,789	100.00%

682 Figure 13 presents the spatial distribution of ecosystem diversity classes based on spatial
 683 complexity for 2024.

684 *Figure 13 Categorization of ecosystem diversity based on spatial complexity by quadrats –*
 685 *2024*
 686

687

688 **4.4 Change detection**

689 We analyse changes in spatial and thematic ecosystem complexity between 2019 and 2024
 690 using a $\pm 10\%$ deviation threshold. Based on this criterion, quadrats are classified into three
 691 categories reflecting different trajectories of change.

692 Quadrats showing more than a 10% decrease in connectivity are classified as critical vulnerable
 693 zones. Quadrats with changes within the $\pm 10\%$ interval are classified as stagnant zones.
 694 Quadrats exhibiting more than a 10% increase in connectivity are classified as improving zones.

695 At national scale, 84.58% of quadrats exhibit a connectivity decrease greater than 10%, while
 696 0.15% show an increase above this threshold. The remaining 15.28% fall within the stagnation
 697 category.

698 Approximately 52% of quadrats show a 10–20% decrease, while around one quarter fall within
 699 the 20–30% decrease class.

700 Figure 14 summarises connectivity change classes between 2019 and 2024, overlaid on a BING
 701 satellite mosaic.

702
 703 Legend:

Symbol	Categories of change between 2019-2024	Quadrat (nr)	Quadrat (%)
	Connectivity decrease > 10%	3,444	84.58%
	Connectivity increase > 10%	6	0.15%
	Tendency of stagnating	622	15.28%
	Sum	4,072	100.00%

704 *Figure 14 Changes of the connectivity indicator between 2019 and 2024,*
 705 *with a BING satellite image mosaic in the background*

706 Given that no substantial difference was observed between 2023 and 2024, the temporal change
 707 analysis is based on comparison between 2019 and 2024.

708 Changes in LPIS boundary structure are derived exclusively from detectable differences in
709 orthophoto interpretation. Boundary removal occurs only where no visible land cover transition
710 remains between adjacent polygons. This includes cases where agricultural practices become
711 homogenised across former boundaries, where temporary infrastructure such as dirt roads
712 disappears or is rerouted, where field margins or semi-natural patches are removed, and where
713 new land cover classes (e.g. afforestation) introduce new boundary structures.

714 Across the study period, the total eligible area remains largely stable. Observed changes are
715 therefore primarily expressed through boundary dynamics rather than area variation.

716 5 Discussion and policy implications

717 The results support the hypothesis that landscape heterogeneity and boundary complexity are
718 associated with biodiversity-relevant structural proxies (Tews et al., 2004; Rybicki et al., 2019).
719 In particular, the boundary length indicator captures a key structural property of agricultural
720 landscapes, namely the intensity of transitions between land cover types. This is consistent with
721 the ecological concept of edge effects, where ecotones can support elevated species richness
722 due to the coexistence of adjacent habitat conditions (Patton, 1975; Tews et al., 2004).

723 However, interpretation of boundary-based indicators requires caution. While increased edge
724 density may reflect higher structural heterogeneity and potentially support generalist or edge-
725 associated species, it may also indicate fragmentation processes that can negatively affect
726 species dependent on large and contiguous habitats (Rybicki et al., 2019; Ogden, 2015).
727 Accordingly, boundary length should not be interpreted as a unidirectional proxy for ecological
728 quality, but rather in conjunction with compositional and intra-parcel indicators.

729 The compositional diversity indicator (B), integrating land cover categories and crop types,
730 provides a proxy for landscape-level heterogeneity. Conceptually, it aligns with classical
731 diversity metrics such as Shannon and Simpson indices (Magurran, 2004; Maskell et al., 2019),
732 although it operates at a coarser thematic resolution constrained by administrative and EO data
733 structures. A key implication is that harmonised categorical information derived from
734 administrative systems can capture meaningful spatial variation when applied consistently at
735 national scale.

736 The mosaicity indicator (C), derived from EO-based segmentation of Sentinel-2 time series,
737 adds an additional layer by capturing intra-parcel heterogeneity. This represents a
738 methodological advancement compared to traditional LPIS approaches, which assume within-
739 parcel homogeneity. The results show that within-parcel variability linked to soil conditions,
740 moisture stress, and management differences can be systematically detected using high-
741 resolution temporal EO data (Gomasasca et al., 2024). This is particularly relevant for precision
742 agriculture and adaptive management strategies, where fine-scale variability increasingly
743 determines spatial patterns of land use intensity.

744 Indicators related to water and vegetation dynamics further highlight the importance of
745 temporal variability in shaping agricultural landscape structure. Periodic waterlogging and
746 moisture fluctuations contribute to habitat diversity but may also reflect stress conditions
747 associated with climatic variability or management constraints. These dynamics therefore
748 require contextual interpretation within broader agro-ecological and climatic conditions.

749 A central strength of the proposed framework lies in the integration of administrative
750 LPIS/IACS data with Earth Observation datasets. LPIS provides stable, policy-relevant spatial
751 delineation, while EO ensures temporal continuity and observational consistency. Their
752 combination enables the derivation of scalable indicators that are operationally implementable

753 while remaining ecologically interpretable. The Hungarian case benefits from wall-to-wall
754 LPIS coverage; however, the approach remains transferable to other Member States using
755 alternative datasets such as Copernicus High Resolution Layers, albeit potentially with reduced
756 thematic detail.

757 Several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the indicators represent indirect structural
758 proxies and do not measure biodiversity in a strict ecological sense. Species richness,
759 abundance, and community composition are not directly observed, and the relationship between
760 structural indicators and biological responses may vary across taxa and landscapes (Magurran,
761 2004). Second, uncertainties inherent in administrative datasets—particularly farmer-declared
762 crop information in the GSA—may propagate into derived indicators, although integration with
763 Area Monitoring System (AMS) outputs is expected to progressively reduce this limitation.
764 Third, the framework does not establish causal relationships between landscape structure and
765 biodiversity outcomes. The indicators capture spatial correlations and structural change but
766 cannot disentangle interacting drivers such as climate variability, soil properties, and
767 management intensity. Addressing causality would require integration with field-based
768 ecological observations and experimental or longitudinal ecological datasets.

769 From a policy perspective, the primary value of the approach lies in its scalability,
770 reproducibility, and direct compatibility with existing administrative systems. Even as proxies,
771 the indicators enable consistent benchmarking across parcels, farms, and regions, which is
772 essential for performance-based agricultural policy design. They provide a transparent basis for
773 identifying areas with higher ecological potential or greater need for restoration and for
774 monitoring spatially explicit policy impacts over time.

775 Finally, the framework demonstrates the potential for integrating biodiversity-relevant
776 monitoring into agricultural control systems through combined use of EO and administrative
777 data. Future developments may enhance indicator sensitivity through inclusion of functional,
778 phenological, or machine learning-derived features. However, such extensions require careful
779 methodological validation to ensure interpretability and consistency in policy applications.

780 6 Conclusions

781 Agricultural policy mechanisms are a primary driver of landscape structure and land use
782 dynamics, with direct implications for biodiversity outcomes. Management intensity, crop
783 choice and diversity, and the maintenance of landscape elements jointly shape the ecological
784 condition of agricultural systems.

785 Current incentive structures combining efficiency-oriented production and area-based
786 payments are associated with the reduction of semi-natural landscape elements (e.g. hedgerows,
787 tree lines, field margins, ditches, and seasonal water features). These changes coincide with
788 increasing field sizes and reduced crop diversity, indicating a simplification of agricultural
789 landscapes.

790 The Hungarian LPIS (MePAR) provides a unique wall-to-wall, high-resolution national land
791 cover dataset explicitly aligned with CAP implementation logic. This enables consistent
792 derivation of spatially explicit ecosystem-relevant indicators and supports large-scale
793 monitoring of landscape structure.

794 Earth Observation (EO) and machine learning-based methods, including crop classification,
795 vegetation signal analysis, and segmentation approaches, provide scalable and objective tools
796 for capturing temporal dynamics in agricultural landscapes. Operational applications within the

797 Area Monitoring System (AMS) demonstrate their potential for deriving indicators of structural
798 heterogeneity, monitoring risk, and supporting spatial targeting of interventions.

799 Across indicators, reduced landscape heterogeneity (mosaicity and connectivity) is consistently
800 associated with simplified habitat structure, which is generally linked to declines in
801 biodiversity-relevant proxies such as species diversity and abundance patterns. Conversely,
802 increases in structural diversity are expected to support more complex ecological conditions
803 and improved biodiversity outcomes.

804 Overall, the proposed framework demonstrates that integrating LPIS and EO data provides a
805 robust, scalable basis for monitoring agricultural landscape structure and its ecological
806 implications in a policy-relevant and reproducible manner.

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Title:

Operational biodiversity proxy indicators derived from LPIS and Earth Observation data: a transferable monitoring framework

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